

Original Article

Hearing Voices: The value of experiential learning - a student seminar

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I recently viewed a brief but poignant documentary concerning the experience of hearing voices - 'What it's like to hear voices' [1]. The discussion explores ways that hearing voices impacts on the lives of individuals and families and ways each attempts to cope with their difficulties.

According to NHS choices (2018):

'Hearing voices in the mind are the most common type of hallucination in people with mental health conditions such as schizophrenia. The voices can be critical, complementary or neutral, and may make potentially harmful commands or engage the person in conversation. They may give a running commentary on the person's actions' [2].

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Hearing voices or auditory hallucinations can have various causes, including the use of certain drugs, alcohol or grief, and trauma. Sometimes we may hear our name called while falling off to sleep. This is typically referred to as hypnagogic and is not considered a departure from reality.

'Hearing voices: An educational seminar

I recall some years back working in a prominent university in the North-west of England. I was responsible for delivering a psychotherapy unit of study to a group of mental health students, which was assessed in formative ways.

Teaching methods ranged from formal didactic lectures, visits to clinical areas, seminars, conducted by practicing psychotherapists, library study and experiential methods of learning.

'Experiential learning is the type of education that occurs when students actively participate and interact with their surroundings. Originally proposed in the 1930's, the application of experiential learning as part of the higher education process has been growing exponentially since Kolb introduced his Experiential Learning Model in the 1970s [3,4].

Kolb proposed an experiential learning cycle, which consists of four components. These are as follows:

1. Concrete or real-world experience, (safe but realistic situations that offer learning opportunities).
2. Reflection on the experience, (what, so what, now what?).
3. Abstract conceptualisation, (what did we achieve, and could we do anything differently. How does our experience match with theories?)
4. Active experimentation, (how can we develop our learning in safe

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Received: 01 Oct 2023

Accepted: 07 Oct 2023

Published: 13 Oct 2023

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and practical ways. How might they apply to other situations?).

Experience - reflection - conceptualise - and modify - (active experimentation) [3]

Kolb also suggested, that learners will have individual learning styles and study preferences and will lean toward some aspects of the learning cycle more than others.

Various authors however have challenged the notion of learning styles suggesting there is no scientific evidence underpinning the ideas [5].

There does appear to be consensus that learners will bring different talents and abilities to educational settings, which can and should be harnessed to the benefit of learning and development.

According to [6], Carl Rogers similarly contributed to the development of experiential learning. Much like like Rogers' theoretical approach to counselling, the ideas are predicated on core principles or conditions:

These are as follows:

- Learning is accelerated when the student is interested in the subject matter.
- Where the subject matter is perceived as threatening to the learner (e.g., the need to change his/her behavior or attitude about strongly held perceptions), learning is accelerated if external (threatening) factors are eliminated or reduced.
- Learning that has been self-initiated by the learner will prove to be more effective than learning that's forced, without a choice for the learner) [6].

[6], also indicates that, according to Rogers, deep learning only takes place when there is an appropriate mix of personal, social, and practical challenges for the learner but holds potential to be incorporated into e-learning methods of tuition - increasingly a popular method of distance learning.

Experiential learning methods applied

Throughout the psychotherapy unit of study, all students became familiar with reflective and experiential learning approaches and the potential benefits. Together, we devised a method of assessment that would go beyond meeting the needs of the curriculum and provide each with opportunities for situational leadership along with the experience of presenting their work at a national conference.

Once familiar with the process of conference attendance and presentation, each would possess the ability to submit their work for conference presentation both nationally and internationally as well as guiding colleagues in clinical areas.

Students from various groups prepared their presentations (usually theatrical) and submitted their work to a mental health conference. Various presentations proved a great success including the psychological ideas of transactional analysis, person-centered psychotherapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, and gestalt theory.

All were delivered in novel ways, which pleased and engaged the audience of mainly mental health practitioners, counsellors, and psychotherapists of different disciplines.

Hearing voices

One presentation, however, stood out. Not because it was better prepared or presented but for its subject matter - hearing voices. While a group of students presented a formal presentation to the audience, two hid behind a screen. At various pre-planned times in the formal presentation, they would shout out - occasionally assertively.

This was a cause of distraction to the audience and at one point the editor of a mental health journal left his seat and admonished the students for their impoliteness. He returned to his seat and the students continued to interrupt the formal presentation.

At a point near the end of the formal presentation, the disruptive students revealed themselves to the audience and explained that this was a pre-planned event designed to provide the experience of hearing voices and the disruption caused to individual attention.

Ethical concerns were addressed prior to the presentation, which was well-received and was, later, the topic of much constructive discussion among the audience.

So, what did we learn?

Group work and experiential methods of learning are potent formats when addressing mental health concerns and group members bring their own talents to making presentations successful. There are opportunities for mutual support, affirmation, and positional leadership and so group members are provided with opportunities to demonstrate knowledge, talents, and abilities - not immediately evident in formal academic and clinical settings.

In addition, formal methods of appraisal and assessment would benefit from recognizing the already established competencies that mental health student's counsellors and psychotherapists, of all disciplines, bring to mental health settings. These include educational programs of study - utilizing both their established and developing abilities in clinical work with patients.

Group work in clinical settings

Students might gain from small group work such as discussion, art, sports, drama, poetry, and reading forums, in fact, any method that harnesses creative approaches to considering mental health and mental ill-health.

Traditional methods of treatment and care can prove dry and unappealing but also have the potential to endorse a sense of inequality between those receiving treatment and care for mental ill-health and those providing services.

My experiences of working in varied mental health settings along with general hospital wards suggest that creative approaches to treatment and

care can prove inclusive and reduce a sense of stigma and shame - so often unknowingly invoked in mental health professionals, patients, and their families.

Many people referred for assessment for psychotherapy may not be in a position to utilise conversational approaches to therapy and 'Visual approaches such as art psychotherapy often prove invaluable.'

The 'Hearing Voices' network and 'Mad Pride organization' [7,8], are predicated on social, experiential and creative approaches to addressing mental ill-health outside of traditional methods and have much to offer to our understanding of the value of collective and unorthodox strategies to the treatment and care of people experiencing mental ill-health - but also learning to live alongside difficulties.

Conclusion

Experiential learning allows students to actively participate, reflect and modify their approach to learning. It is a learning strategy suitable throughout healthcare curricula - including counselling and psychotherapy units of study. The method discussed in this paper was devised by students to allow conference delegates to themselves experience the cognitive disruption of hearing voices.

According to the NHS choices (2018)

'The experience [of hearing voices] is usually very distressing, but it's not always negative. Some people who hear voices are able to live with them and get used to them or may consider them a part of their life. It's not uncommon for recently bereaved people to hear voices, and this may sometimes be the voice of their loved one' [2].

However, they also recommend:

'If you're hearing voices, discuss any concerns you have with your GP. This is important in determining whether you have a serious mental illness' [2]. Your GP can arrange for a more specialised assessment should it be required.'

While term mental illness has become contentious in recent years because of the potential to overlook psychosocial antecedents to mental ill-health - the advice is both safe and sensible.

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Cite this article: Alun Charles Jones. (2023) Hearing Voices: The value of experiential learning - a student seminar. Archives of Clinical Case Studies and Case Reports 4(3): 333- 335.

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